

Congenital Ileal Stenosis in Children: Comparative Surgical Management with Resection and Ileal Plasty

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Introduction

Congenital ileal stenoses represent an important cause of intestinal obstruction in the pediatric population. This paper analyzes the clinical manifestations and surgical management of two cases of incomplete ileal diaphragm, with challenges in differential diagnosis.

Materials and methods

In the first case, a 1 year and 7-month-old patient presented with alimentary vomiting, later becoming bilious, fever, and dehydration, in the context of acute rhinopharyngitis. Persistence of symptoms and the change in the character of vomiting required further investigations. Abdominal ultrasound revealed distended intestinal loops and air-fluid levels in the left hypochondrium. The definitive diagnosis was established intraoperatively through exploratory laparotomy: ileal stenosis with incomplete diaphragm. The second case involves a 3-year-old patient who presented with periumbilical abdominal pain, vomiting and absence of stool passage for 2 days. CT revealed distended intestinal loops, with several air-fluid levels. The distal ileal loops appeared collapsed, with computed tomography confirming the presence of a partial stenosis that allowed survival up to this age.

Results

In the first case, the obstruction was localized at the ileal level. A segmental enterectomy was performed, followed by a diamond-shaped ileo-ileal anastomosis, ensuring adequate luminal caliber and continuity. In the second case, the ileal diaphragm was excised, and ileal plasty was carried out. This approach effectively relieved the obstruction while preserving bowel length. The postoperative course was favorable in both cases, with progressive resumption of oral feeding and no early complications.

Conclusion

The particularity of these cases lies in their late clinical presentation and highlights two different surgical approaches: resection with anastomosis versus management through excision of the obstruction and plasty, the difference being determined by the severity of the stenosis, caliber discrepancy, and viability of the intestinal segment. In conclusion, therapeutic success depends on adapting the surgical technique to the specific anatomy of the lesion.

Keywords

congenital ileal stenosis, obstruction, incomplete diaphragm